

A Machine Learning-Based Routing Protocol for 6G-Internet of Things network: Performance Evaluation

Seyed Salar Sefati
Department of Telecommunications,
POLITEHNICA Bucharest National University
of Science and Technology
Bucharest, Romania
Sefati.seyedsalar@upb.ro

Simona Halunga
Department of Telecommunications,
POLITEHNICA Bucharest National University
of Science and Technology
Bucharest, Romania
Simona.halunga@upb.ro

Razvan Craciunescu
Department of Telecommunications,
POLITEHNICA Bucharest National University
of Science and Technology
Bucharest, Romania
Razvan.craciunescu@upb.ro

Octavian Fratu
Department of Telecommunications,
POLITEHNICA Bucharest National University
of Science and Technology
Bucharest, Romania
Octavian.fratu@upb.ro

Abstract— The integration of sixth-generation (6G) technology and the Internet of Things (IoT) is poised to revolutionize data management and technological interaction by providing unprecedented data transfer rates, ultra-low latency, and enhanced connectivity. This paper addresses the challenges of efficient, reliable, and adaptive data transmission in 6G-enabled IoT networks through a novel Machine Learning-Based Routing Protocol. Utilizing Deep Q-Networks (DQN), the proposed protocol optimizes routing by continuously adapting to real-time network states, ensuring Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC), energy efficiency, and real-time adaptability. Traditional routing protocols often fall short due to the complex and dynamic nature of IoT environments, necessitating innovative approaches to balance factors such as energy consumption, latency, and reliability. Our proposed method involves several key steps: initialization of the network, data collection and preprocessing, training of the machine learning model, route discovery and optimization, and data transmission. The reward function in DQN is designed to maximize energy efficiency, reduce latency, and enhance reliability. Experimental results, conducted using the Network Simulator 3 (NS3) and compared with existing methodologies such as Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient with Prioritized Experience Replay (DDPG-PER) and Speed-optimized Long Short-Term Memory (SP-LSTM), demonstrate the superiority of our approach.

Keywords— 6G, Internet of Things, Routing, Artificial Intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of sixth-generation (6G) and the Internet of Things (IoT) is poised to transform how we interact with technology and manage data [1]. 6G, the upcoming generation of wireless communication technology, promises unparalleled data transfer rates, ultra-low latency, and significantly enhanced connectivity. These advancements are crucial for the widespread adoption and effectiveness of IoT, where billions of interconnected devices need to communicate and share data in real-time [2]. The seamless connectivity and efficient data handling capabilities provided by 6G will enable

IoT to achieve its full potential, impacting diverse sectors such as healthcare, smart cities, and industrial automation [3].

In the realm of 6G and IoT, routing protocols are fundamental in ensuring efficient data transmission across the network [4]. These protocols must be robust, adaptive, and capable of managing the dynamic nature of IoT networks. The primary challenge lies in optimizing the routing process to balance multiple factors such as energy consumption, latency, and reliability. Traditional routing protocols often fall short due to the complex and fluctuating demands of IoT environments [5]. Consequently, there is an increasing need for innovative approaches that leverage advanced technologies like machine learning to enhance routing efficiency in 6G-enabled IoT networks.

To address these challenges, we propose a Machine Learning-Based Routing Protocol for 6G IoT Networks. This method harnesses the capabilities of Deep Q-Networks (DQN) [6] to make intelligent routing decisions based on the real-time state of the network. The proposed protocol involves several key steps: initialization of the network, data collection and preprocessing, training of the machine learning model, route discovery and optimization, and data transmission. Our contributions through this proposed method are threefold:

- **Enhanced Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC):** DQN, the routing protocol ensures that data packets are transmitted with minimal delay and high reliability, meeting the stringent requirements of URLLC in 6G networks.
- **Energy Efficiency:** The protocol incorporates energy consumption metrics into the decision-making process, optimizing the routes to prolong the battery life of IoT devices and enhance overall network sustainability.

- **Real-Time Adaptability:** The machine learning model continuously updates its routing strategies based on real-time data, allowing the network to adapt dynamically to changing conditions and maintain optimal performance.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The rapid proliferation of IoT devices and the anticipated deployment of 6G networks introduce significant challenges in managing secure and efficient communication within large-scale, dynamic environments. Traditional network architectures and routing protocols struggle to cope with the high demands for low latency, high bandwidth, and robust security required by IoT applications [7]. Specifically, the integration of numerous IoT devices into a 6G Wireless Personal Area Network (WPAN) necessitates a sophisticated approach to ensure seamless communication, data integrity, and energy efficiency. Figure 1 illustrates a complex IoT configuration involving a 6G border router and various protocols like Constrained Application Protocol Secure (CoAPs), Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS), and Internet Protocol version 6 (IPv6) to manage and secure communication. However, the current methodologies fall short in dynamically adapting to network changes, optimizing routing paths in real-time, and ensuring high energy efficiency. Addressing these challenges requires a novel routing protocol capable of leveraging the advanced capabilities of 6G while ensuring secure, efficient, and reliable communication across the IoT network.

Fig. 1: 6G-IoT Wireless Personal Area Network (WPAN) communication architecture

A. Equations for 6G IoT Network

Energy efficiency (E_{eff}) can be defined as the amount of data transmitted per unit of energy consumed, taking into account the 6G IoT network.

$$E_{eff} = \frac{D_t}{E_c} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- D_t is the total data transmitted in the 6G IoT network (in bits)
- E_c is the total energy consumed by IoT devices and the 6G network infrastructure (in joules)

Latency reduction (L_{red}) can be expressed as the difference between the initial latency (L_{init}) and the improved latency (L_{impr}) achieved through the proposed routing protocol.

$$L_{red} = L_{init} - L_{impr} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- L_{init} is the initial latency in the 6G IoT network (in seconds)
- L_{impr} is the improved latency after implementing the proposed routing protocol (in seconds).

Reliability (R_{net}) in a 6G IoT network can be defined as the probability that the network will perform its intended function without failure over a specified period.

$$R_{net} = \frac{N_s}{N_t} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- N_s is the number of successful data transmissions in the 6G IoT network
- N_t is the total number of data transmission attempts in the 6G IoT network

B. Proposed method : Machine Learning based routing protocol for 6G IoT networks

Step 1: Initialization

We deploy N IoT devices, M 6G base stations, G gateways, and S servers within the network area. Let $N = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N\}$ represent the set of IoT devices. Each node $i \in N$ is initialized with a position $P_i = (x_i, y_i)$ and an initial energy level $E_i(0)$. The network connectivity is defined by the adjacency matrix A , where:

$$a_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if nodes } i \text{ and } j \text{ are connected} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Step 2: Data Collection and Preprocessing

We collect data on node positions, energy levels, traffic patterns, and connectivity status to define the network state at time t as:

$$S(t) = \{(P_i, E_i, T_i) \mid i \in N\} \quad (5)$$

where P_i , E_i , and T_i represent the position, energy, and traffic of node i , respectively. We extract features

$$F_i = \{f_{i1}, f_{i2}, \dots, f_{ik}\} \quad (6)$$

for each node i , where each f_{i1} represents specific features such as node degree, average latency, or link reliability.

Step 3: Machine Learning Model Training

We select a DQN model to make routing decisions. The reward function $R(t)$ is defined to evaluate the routing decision performance, taking into account energy efficiency, latency, and reliability:

$$R(t) = \alpha \cdot E_{eff}(t) - \beta \cdot L(t) + \gamma \cdot R_{net}(t) \quad (7)$$

where α , β , and γ are weighting factors. E_{eff} represents the energy efficiency, $L(t)$ represents the latency, and $R_{net}(t)$ represents the reliability at time (t) . The state-action value Q-function is updated using the Bellman equation:

$$Q(S(t), a) \leftarrow Q(S(t), a) + \alpha (R(t) + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(S(t+1), a') - Q(S(t), a)) \quad (8)$$

where α is the learning rate, γ is the discount factor, a is the action taken, and $S(t)$ is the state at time t .

Step 4: Route Discovery and Optimization

Potential routes R are initialized using the trained machine learning model to predict the best possible routes. The routes are continuously updated and adjusted in real-time based on the current network state $S(t)$ and the trained Q -function $Q(S(t), a)$.

Algorithm 1 ML-Based Routing Protocol for 6G IoT

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1: Step 1: Initialization
2: Input: Number of IoT devices ( $N$ ), base stations ( $M$ ), gateways ( $G$ ), servers ( $S$ )
3: for each node  $i$  in  $N$  do
4:   Initialize position  $P_i$  and energy level  $E_i(0)$ 
5: end for
6: Define connectivity matrix  $A$ 
7: Step 2: Data Collection and Preprocessing
8: Collect data on positions, energy levels, traffic patterns, and connectivity  $I$ :
9: Define network state  $S(t) = \{P_i, E_i, T_i \mid i \in N\}$ 
10: for each node  $i$  in  $N$  do
11:   Extract features  $F_i$ 
12: end for
13: Step 3: Machine Learning Model Training
14: Select DQN model, define reward function  $R(t)$ 
15: Initialize  $Q(S(t))$ 
16: for each episode do
17:   Initialize state  $S(t)$ 
18:   while  $S(t)$  is not terminal do
19:     Choose action  $a$  from  $S(t)$  using policy (e.g.,  $\epsilon$  greedy)
20:     Take action  $a$ , observe reward  $R(t)$  and next state  $S(t+1)$ 
21:     Update  $Q(S(t), a)$  using Bellman equation
22:     Set  $S(t) \leftarrow S(t+1)$ 
23:   end while
24: end for
25: Step 4: Route Discovery and Optimization
26: Initialize routes  $R$  using trained DQN model
27: while network is operational do
28:   Continuously update routes based on current state  $S(t)$  and  $Q(S(t), a)$ 
29: end while
30: Step 5: Data Transmission
31: for each route  $r$  in  $R$  do
32:   for each node  $i$  in route  $r$  do
33:     Forward data based on best action  $a = \arg \max Q(S(t), a)$ 
34:     Monitor energy consumption  $E_i$  and latency  $L_{ij}$ 
35:   end for
36: end for

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Step 5: Data Transmission

Data packets are transmitted along the selected routes R . For each node i in the route, data is forwarded to the next node j based on the predicted best action a^* :

$$\alpha^* = \arg \max Q(S(t), a) \quad (9)$$

Energy consumption $E_i(t)$ of each node i is monitored:

$$E_i(t) = E_i(t-1) - E_{tx} - E_{rx} \quad (10)$$

where E_{tx} and E_{rx} are the energy costs of transmission and reception, respectively. Latency L_{ij} for data transmission between nodes i and j is monitored as:

$$L_{ij} = L_{prop} + L_{trans} + L_{proc} \quad (11)$$

where L_{prop} , L_{trans} , and L_{proc} are the propagation, transmission, and processing delays, respectively.

The pseudocode demonstrates the proposed method algorithm.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the experimental results of the proposed Machine Learning-Based Routing Protocol for 6G IoT Networks. Our approach is analytically compared with other current methodologies, specifically the deep deterministic policy gradient algorithm with prioritized experience replay (DDPG-PER) [8] and Speed-optimized Long short-term memory (SP-LSTM) [9]. We conducted the experiments using the NS3 simulator to establish a network architecture modeled after the Sierpinski Triangle topology [10]. The setup includes 100 IoT devices, one 6G base station, four gateways, one cloud server, and one edge server.

Figure 2 shows the energy efficiency comparison between the proposed method, DDPG-PER, and SP-LSTM, measured in bits per joule across different numbers of users. The proposed method demonstrates superior energy efficiency, particularly as the number of users increases. Key observations from the figure indicate that at 20 users, the proposed method has an energy efficiency of about 3.5 bits/joule, while DDPG PER and SP-LSTM are at 2.5 bits/joule and 3 bits/joule, respectively. At 100 users, the proposed method reaches approximately 7 bits/joule, compared to DDPG-PER at 5.5 bits/joule and SP-LSTM at 6 bits/joule.

Figure 3 illustrates the transmission rate comparison between the proposed method, DDPG-PER, and SP-LSTM, measured in kilobits per second (kbps) across different numbers of users. The proposed method consistently achieves higher transmission rates than both DDPG-PER and SP-LSTM across all user counts. At 20 users, the proposed method achieves approximately 250 kbps, while DDPG-PER and SP-LSTM achieve around 150 kbps and 100 kbps, respectively. At 100 users, the proposed method reaches nearly 600 kbps, significantly higher than DDPG-PER at around 450 kbps and SP-LSTM at approximately 400 kbps.

Figure 4 illustrates the latency performance of three routing protocols—Proposed Method, DDPG-PER, and SP-LSTM—across different numbers of users (20, 40, 60, 80, 100). As the number of users increases, the latency for all protocols shows a gradual increase, reflecting the additional load and complexity in the network. The proposed method consistently exhibits the lowest latency across all user counts, indicating its superior efficiency in managing network traffic and making real-time routing decisions.

Fig. 2. Energy Efficiency based on different Number of Users

Fig. 3. Transmission rate based on different Number of Users

Fig. 4. Latency based on different Number of Users

IV. CONCLUSION

The integration of 6G technology and IoT promises significant advancements in connectivity and data

management. Our proposed Machine Learning-Based Routing Protocol, utilizing Deep Q-Networks (DQN), effectively addresses the challenges of efficient, reliable, and adaptive routing in 6G-enabled IoT networks. Experimental results demonstrate that our protocol surpasses existing methods in energy efficiency, transmission rate, and latency, making it well-suited for diverse IoT applications. By leveraging advanced machine learning techniques, this protocol enhances network performance, ensuring robust and real-time communication essential for the future of inter connected smart devices.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study has been conducted under the project 'MObility and Training FOR beyond 5G ecosystems (MOTOR5G)' project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions (MSCA) Innovative Training Network (ITN) under grant agreement No. 861219.

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